

Theoretical aspects of organizing mathematical education in elementary school classes

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Annotation

Personal qualities likely to be found in a student - personal dignity, principledness, self-awareness, honesty, independence, curiosity, integrity, and creativity- depend on their activity. Therefore, the effectiveness of a teaching process should not be based solely on didactic methods, but rather, it is necessary to explain it based on the characteristics of a child's activity, even with the introduction of reverse problems.

Key words: education, activity, education and upbringing, monitoring, capability, initial, subject

Negotiation shapes the interaction between the two subjects of education. Viewing education as an equal subject alongside the teacher, exploring some ideas in the didactic field, and broadening the possibilities of limiting certain goals that do not align with our national spirit and traditions. For example, in contemporary educational theory, the organization, management, and monitoring of educational and upbringing activities are essential requirements. If we consider the student as an equal subject to the teacher, then it is appropriate to acknowledge the crucial requirement of coordination in organizing, managing, and monitoring educational and upbringing activities. The student's active participation in shaping and implementing education in collaboration with the teacher is also highly regarded. Furthermore, one of the goals that remains relevant in contemporary educational theory is the idea of fostering social experience. The notion is based on the premise that students with different ages, knowledge levels, working speeds, degrees of independence, thinking styles, and readiness should receive the same material, at the same pace, and sometimes even in the same format. In reality, customization is individual. No matter how skilled a teacher may be, students adapt the information content to their own needs and abilities to varying degrees.

A child begins to develop their social experience from the first day they start school. Initial education is based on synthetic activity, and in its execution, children acquire the foundations of knowledge (related to all subjects), ethics, artistic-aesthetic, vocational, and socio-political activities. Gradually, as they progress to higher grades, the emphasis shifts towards imparting these activity fundamentals in an analytical manner. Consider the process of training agricultural, industrial, literary, and artistic workers in rural areas. If in the early grades, a child is exposed to various forms of activity within the framework of initial education and acquires knowledge related to different professions (e.g., carpentry, medicine, teaching, etc.) in addition to basic information, then various forms of activity are integrated into the knowledge of the respective professions. Furthermore, as children mature and move beyond the initial stages of acquiring knowledge, they develop various aspects of activity, and the process of selecting a profession and nurturing children in that profession becomes linked to the chosen profession in terms of ethical, political, economic, and cultural activities.

In order to equip students with the necessary skills to solve problems, it is essential to teach them how to find relevant connections between different aspects of life and those being explored, just as they are being provided and sought in various real-life situations. Understanding

how students have developed problem-solving skills and how they have internalized independent problem-solving is crucial in acquiring problem-solving skills. These tools include the ability to analyze the problem, outline a solution plan, express the solution in a relevant oral or written format, and verify the correctness of the solution.

In the early grades, fostering creativity in teaching mathematics is of paramount importance. This is because each task that is creatively designed relies on the teacher's creative skills on one hand and on the other hand, it depends on students' independent work and creative activities. The completion of every creative task in mathematics implies the development of independent thinking skills in students, highlighting the fact that problem-solving in each creative context is shaped as a skill.

In the early grades, educational subjects offer ample opportunities to introduce and resolve contradictions. For instance, in mathematics, addition and subtraction, multiplication and division, in natural sciences, day and night, winter and summer, solid and liquid, shape and content, the symbol and the movement of an object, all provide examples of such contradictions. Bringing these contradictions to the surface and resolving them involves creating independent tasks, performing assignments, and solving problems that place the child in a problematic or task-oriented situation. Facing a problematic situation on the right side fosters active, independent thinking in the child, encouraging them to address the contradictions presented on the right side. This form of education enhances children's understanding, inviting them to engage in creative activities. The positive and useful contradictions resolved in the learning process lead to subjective discoveries - new knowledge.

In classroom activities, presenting information in a contrasting manner, i.e., on the basis of opposition or contradiction, plays a crucial role in enhancing students' knowledge. The topic of "Comparing Fractions" in a 3rd-grade mathematics lesson is introduced based on this concept of imagination.

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